

A STUDY OF THE EFFECTS OF ENVIRONMENTAL AWARENESS ON PURCHASE INTENTION OF GREEN PRODUCTS IN URBAN RAJASTHAN

Mankeshva Saini

Research scholar, Department of Management Studies, Rajasthan Technical University Kota,

Dr Pankaj Jain

Principal, B.J.S Rampuria Jain College, Bikaner

Abstract

Consumers are now more aware than ever about the impact their choices have on the ecosystem. Being environmentally aware involves appreciating the significance of one's natural surroundings. It thus demonstrates consciousness of and determination to address environmental problems. Consumers' views on living sustainably have shifted. The human race is making concerted efforts to lessen its destructive effects on the planet. This, nevertheless, is not common and remains in the process of developing. Today, practically every nation and community has become more conscious of the environmental concerns that need to be addressed. Strong evidence suggests that environmentally conscious consumer behaviour emerges out of empathy for the natural world. However, there hasn't been a lot of progress in raising consumers' understanding of the benefits of using eco-friendly items. Marketers have been touting their eco-friendly credentials to set their products apart and increase consumer retention. Researching customers' understanding and mindset towards adopting green practices is crucial for making a significant effect with the green concept. The current study aims to investigate the environmental consciousness of urban residents in the Indian state of Rajasthan, with a particular focus on their attitudes towards environmentally friendly goods and practices.

Keywords: environmentally conscious, green consumers, green purchasing intention (GPI), consumers' understanding, sustainable products, eco-friendly, green items

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1. Introduction

The way people consume within the globe currently isn't viable, which has led to serious environmental issues like pollution, loss of natural supplies, rising greenhouse gas releases, as well as climate change (Ansu-Mensah, 2021). These problems have contributed to the procedure of 'going green' as well as, in the end, to more people being conscious of and purchasing sustainable products. Green is frequently linked with concepts like ethical consumption, sustainable marketing, environmentally concerned customers, social obligation, natural, viable, and environmentally favourable or pro-environmental. Within many wealthy nations, green products are considered the most dependable way to protect the earth (Ansu-Mensah, 2021). The worth of sustainable products possesses a big effect on people's and the planet's improvement and progress. Furthermore, even though people are becoming more conscious about sustainable products within developed countries, this knowledge is still low within developing nations (Ansu-Mensah, 2021). Because of this, people in developing economies are worried, and companies are trying to maintain their consumers by setting green marketing goals.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Green consumerism

The idea regarding the 'green consumer' is now the fulcrum within which marketers and researchers have centred their environmental marketing approaches. According to do Paço, Shiel and Alves (2019), green consumers or GC represent the customers who exert considerable effort to prevent acquiring possibly hazardous goods. GCs are additionally defined as individuals who prevent any item that causes adverse effects to living organisms and degrades the natural world during production or usage. Furthermore, GCs are regarded as customers who are environmentally conscious and committed as well as knowledgeable about environmental problems (Amberg and Fogarassy, 2019). GCs are individuals who value perceived behavioural control along with green advertising. Even though the costs of green items may be considerably more expensive than those of conventional products, GCs continue to purchase them due to the prospective long-term benefits (Paço, Shiel and Alves, 2019). Additionally, GCs contemplate the impact of their purchases on others, distinguishing them from typical customers. In addition, the existence of GCs suggests the need for sustainable marketing.

2.2 Environment Consciousness

Golob and Kronegger (2019) stated that individual responsibility for the ecosystem is regarded as the most basic factor in environmental studies. Environmental awareness cultivates an appreciation for preserving the ecosystem, and individuals with an elevated awareness are more inclined to buy green items than those with a low awareness (Trudel, 2019). Environmental awareness refers to the significance of the surroundings to people. It also demonstrates a cognizance of environmental problems and an intention to take action to address them (Zhang *et al.*, 2020). Environment information has an important effect on an individual's ecological behaviour (Trudel, 2019). Consumers gain environmental knowledge through the green efforts undertaken by businesses. Less consumer understanding of environmental issues provides ample opportunity to investigate the connection between environmental consciousness along with green consumption behaviour (Golob and Kronegger, 2019).

2.3 Green purchase intention

It is important to note that customers' intentions play a significant role in promotional tactics. Purchasing intention relates to what customers contemplate and intend to buy. Consumers' behavioural intention refers to the potential behaviours that induce customers' dedication or desire to buy a specific product (Zhuang, Luo and Riaz, 2021). Additionally, behavioural

intention can be described as signs of the extent to which individuals are prepared to put in, or the amount of exertion they intend to generate, in executing the behaviour (Zaremohzzabieh *et al.*, 2021). Furthermore, ecological motives, including the search for healthier alternatives, environmental awareness, and sustainable development, influence consumer purchasing decisions. According to Nguyen *et al.* (2019), a shift in consumer behaviour is frequently influenced by market trends. Personal marketing behaviour enables customers to compare the durability, cost, value, and accessibility of competing products. Zhuang, Luo and Riaz, (2021) suggested that to promote an eco-friendly lifestyle, it is necessary to raise awareness and promote the consumption of green items, which will result in a transition from traditional to green items. According to reports, green products possess a significant impact on general green purchasing intentions (Zaremohzzabieh *et al.*, 2021). This green purchase intention or GPI among customers has an outstanding effect on their green purchasing behaviour. As customers are concerned about the natural world, they aim to purchase green products or GPs with the objective not to damage the environment but instead to defend it for future generations. Moreover, consumers' understanding, cost, accessibility, worth, and the standard of green products could have a significant impact on their GPI (Nguyen *et al.*, 2019). Environmentally conscious customers are anxious, willing, and inclined to spend more for environmentally friendly goods when they are aware of the item's green information, outstanding value, superior craftsmanship, functionality, environmental concerns, along with effectiveness (Zhuang, Luo and Riaz, 2021). Therefore, customers should be made aware of green products to encourage their participation within GPI and subsequent green consumption.

3. Research Methodology

This research used interpretivism research philosophy for this particular work because interpretivism is not against the existence of objective reality. Nevertheless, they reject the existence of separately observable reality. Different from positivist philosophy, interpretivism claims that any research has been shaped and affected by the analysts' previous hypotheses and perspectives (Alharahsheh and Pius, 2020).

The research approach used in this research is the deductive research approach. The deductive approach is straightforward as well as simple to grasp, which makes it simple to comprehend the rationale behind an assessment (Woiceshyn and Daellenbach, 2018). The rational framework of the deductive approach is straightforward, rendering the conclusion simple to comprehend. This simplicity also facilitates the detection of any mistakes or lapses in logical thinking.

The research method used here is gathering secondary data from previous research works and analysing those data to present relevant findings for this research. Secondary studies are typically more affordable than primary studies. Since the information already exists, the most significant expense is typically the labour required for finding and interpreting the information (Sileyew, 2019). Secondary research facilitates accessibility to the most effective research methods. Secondary research is capable of being performed independently. In addition, it serves as a great approach to employ before other stages, as it identifies the most effective primary research that needs to be conducted. This precludes duplication of research which is already available to the public (Sileyew, 2019).

4. Results and Discussion

The research conducted by Johri, Vijayvargy, and Gupta (2022) stated that because of the outbreak of COVID-19 within Rajasthan, consumer attitudes and intentions regarding green restaurants are becoming more important, indicating that there remains a great opportunity for businesses within the restaurant sector to tackle these shifts within the food buying as well as consumption habits of individuals once regularity comes back. The worldwide pandemic

presents a vast opportunity to reach the demands of wellness and environmentally conscious customers in Rajasthan, who might prefer the advantages of green practices over the expensive nature of such efforts (Johri, Vijayvargy, and Gupta, 2022). Consequently, businesses must think about how they can render sustainable products accessible to customers at affordable prices while contributing to the development towards a risk-free environment. According to Kautish and Dash (2017), customers from rural Rajasthan are cognizant of environmental concerns, however marketers have likely not completely examined the marketplace for sustainable goods. This research contends firmly that businesses should capitalise on attending the rural marketplace potential within India, especially in Rajasthan. It proved the necessity of customising the marketing formula for rural consumers to determine the behavioural aspects that influence consumer choice (Kautish and Dash, 2017).

Consumers within Gujrat, as well as Rajasthan, are conscious of the adverse impacts of non-green selling and usage, according to Mathur's (2019) study. They are extremely worried about the issue of environmental contamination, the packaging of products (plastic containers), and their negative environmental impacts. Respondents to the research thought that the use of green products saves the ecosystem and the community, and they concurred that these items are functionally preferable. Additionally, they concurred that green items are healthy. The majority of the participants have a favourable view of environmentally friendly items. They hold the opinion that this is essential for products to be environmentally friendly and free of preservatives. While considering purchase decisions, customers believe that sustainability is crucial. In general, they value organic over traditional goods and were pleased with the majority of eco-friendly options (Mathur, 2019). In addition, respondents concurred that they would purchase/consume ecological items. Food items (for example, organic foodstuffs), healthcare items (for example, herbal), soap/detergents (for example, herbal), as well as energy-efficient devices (for example, 5-star rating) such as LEDs are frequently purchased items (Mathur, 2019). Less frequently bought goods include clothing, furniture, as well as environmentally friendly automobiles., Mathur (2019) also reported that participants have an interest in perusing articles about environmentally friendly goods as well as that they devote heed to the opinions of their peers and family regarding eco-friendly items along with eco-friendly initiatives. Customers believe that local businesses and government should collaborate to build a sustainable society. In comparison with participants in Gujarat, participants in Rajasthan tend to be influenced by the opinions of their peers and family when deciding whether or not to purchase environmentally friendly goods (Mathur, 2019). Respondents concurred that companies' claims regarding green products/ingredients are not credible; product content/label details is not accurate. Additionally, consumers have doubts about the materials and dependability of eco-brand products.

5. Conclusion and Future Scope

The responsibility for the community along with the regulatory setting, as well as increasing environmental problems, prompted the investigators to look into the safeguarding of the environment of customers. Customers are cognizant of environmental issues and their detrimental effects. In addition, they were conscious of ecological products but did not understand how they might help the ecosystem. When they were informed, they were willing to buy the item for the main purpose that it would aid in protecting the ecosystem. It is evident from the results mentioned above that ecologically favourable opinions have grown, but because of limited awareness among customers, an extensive percentage of customers remain without "green" understanding. To encourage individuals to evolve into further eco-responsible as well as environmentally conscious for the sake of preserving the planet, initiatives need to be implemented to educate consumers concerning environmentally friendly goods along with sustainable advertising. This study only focuses on the effect of environmental consciousness

on consumers purchasing green products in Rajasthan. Therefore, future research needs to be conducted to evaluate the consumers' perspectives of the overall Indian market. Moreover, primary data can be gathered through interviews or surveys of consumers from different parts of India to increase the scope of further research.

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